

The Effect of Service Quality, Word of Mouth and Perceived Price on Purchase Decisions using Air Conditioner Services Moderated by Customer Satisfaction in Households of Jakarta

(Case Study at PT. Sahabat Karya Teknik)

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Abstract: Case study at PT. Sahabat Karya Teknik, this study intends to examine and analyze the "The effect of service quality, word of mouth, and perceived price on purchase decisions using AC (Air Conditioner) services moderated by customer satisfaction in households of Jakarta. In this study, 175 participants were surveyed using a purposive sample over a 30-day period. The Multiple Linear Regression Model test tool was used with SPSS 23.0 software to assess the hypotheses proposed in this study. Testing various linear regression models reveals that customer satisfaction is significantly influenced by service quality, word of mouth and perceived price variables. Each factor, service quality, word of mouth, perceived price and customer satisfaction has a partial impact on each other.

Keywords: Service Quality, Word of Mouth, Perceived Price, Customer Satisfaction, Purchase Decision.

I. INTRODUCTION

The air in the room can be conditioned with the help of an Air Conditioner (AC) which also has a calming effect on the body (Sofyan, 2010). An important element that can have an impact on health is the air quality in air conditioned rooms (Arjani, 2011). AC is a process of thermodynamic treatment of air to regulate temperature, humidity, cleanliness and distribution simultaneously to achieve comfortable conditions required by its occupants. Its main purpose is to provide a cooling effect, but it also serves to provide a sense of comfort (comfort air conditioner) (Stoecker, 1996).

Psychologically, AC can affect a person's psychological condition. How the mental state and behavior of a person can be affected by AC. For tropical climates, hot temperature and weather conditions psychologically affect the performance of someone who often feels tired quickly.

Indonesia is a country with a humid tropical climate. The characteristics of a humid tropical climate are quite high humidity, namely 70-80% in summer and 80-95% in the rainy season. In addition to high humidity, the air temperature also ranges between 24°C at night and 34°C during the day. These two things affect human thermal comfort. Thermal comfort is a state of mind that expresses satisfaction with its thermal environment.

In tropical countries, AC is needed all the time. In Indonesia, many places and buildings, especially those in urban areas such as offices, restaurants, even homes and schools, are facilitated with AC in every corner of the room. AC is an alternative to natural ventilation so as to increase comfort in activities. This is the reason behind the large number of AC users. Of course, along with the development of economic growth, the Indonesian people are increasing and prosperous, it is possible that there will be more and more enthusiasts of AC in Indonesia, it might even become one of the basic needs of every home.

The location of Indonesia, which is geographically located in an area with a tropical climate, makes many people interested in using AC. The development of the use of AC in Indonesia has had psychological and social impacts on the people who use it. The interest of people who live in the tropics makes AC sales increase every year.

According to data from iesr.or.id (28/8/2018) collected from a study conducted by Lawrence Berkeley National Laboratory in 2013, the growth rate of AC sales in Indonesia exceeds 10-15% per year. The level of consumer needs Air AC is becoming a problem in this situation as it continues to increase. This is evidenced by the 2.5 million AC sold in Indonesia every year. In 2021, the Central Statistics Agency (BPS) reports that an average of 11.1 percent of homes in Indonesia use AC.

Up from 10.28 percent the previous year. According to statistics collected, the number of people using AC is increasing every year. According to BPS 2021 statistics for the Jakarta area, the percentage of houses using AC rises to 2 to 3 percent per year of all households in Jakarta. This shows how the influence of AC on daily life has grown significantly. AC is also used in office buildings which aims to provide comfort for workers so they can work efficiently and more productively and reduce fatigue.

Province	Percentage of Households Using AC by Province				
	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021
DKI Jakarta	30.83%	32.68%	34.84%	36.58%	39.50%
Kepulauan Riau	29.38%	31.14%	33.20%	34.86%	37.65%
Kalimantan Timur	17.91%	18.98%	20.24%	21.25%	22.95%
Banten	15.91%	16.86%	17.98%	18.88%	20.39%
Kep. Bangka Belitung	12.02%	12.74%	13.58%	14.26%	15.40%
Bali	11.83%	12.54%	13.37%	14.04%	15.16%
Riau	10.25%	10.87%	11.58%	12.16%	13.13%
Papua Barat	9.03%	9.57%	10.20%	10.71%	11.57%
Kalimantan Selatan	8.71%	9.23%	9.84%	10.33%	11.16%
Gorontalo	8.53%	9.04%	9.64%	10.12%	10.93%
Average for all of Indonesia	8.66%	9.18%	9.79%	10.28%	11.10%

Table 1: Ten Indonesian Provinces with the Largest Percentage of Households Using AC 2017-2021
Source: Badan Pusat Statistik, 2022

Based on Table 1 above, the proportion of households using AC in Indonesia between 2017-2021 has increased from year to year, this shows that ownership of AC in the Indonesian household sector continues to increase.

Fig. 1: 2018-2021 PT. Sahabat Karya Teknik Sales Graph
Source: Company Internal Data, 2022

Based on Graph1 above, it shows that the annual sales of PT. Sahabat Karya Teknik fluctuate. The graph shows that annual sales from 2018 had revenues of 171,520,000 in 2019 there were revenues of 253,500,000 in 2020 there were revenues of 162,507,600 and in 2021 there were revenues of 212,980,000 resulting in inconsistent annual sales in income per year. PT. Sahabat Karya Teknik's annual sales are also much lower than its service capacity. This service capacity is determined based on the technician's capacity, equipment and

capabilities owned by PT. Sahabat Karya Teknik. This annual sales is of course inversely proportional to the condition of AC users in the household sector in Jakarta, which always experiences an increase based on data from the Badan Pusat Statistik.

No.	Variable	Respondents	Percentage	Accumulation
1	Word of Mouth	28	16%	69%
2	Customer satisfaction	22	13%	
3	Perceived Price	34	20%	
4	Service Quality	34	20%	
5	Brand Image	17	10%	
6	Place Existence	5	3%	
7	Physical Environment	5	3%	
8	Social Influence	9	5%	
9	Lifestyle	10	6%	
10	Offline Advertisement	7	4%	
Total		172	100%	

Table 2: Preliminary Survey Results

This can be seen in table 2 there are 4 top factors chosen by respondents as the main factor consumers decide to use AC services with a composition of 28 respondent which choose Word of Mouth, 22 respondents chose Customer Satisfaction, 34 respondents chose perceived price and 34 respondents chose service quality. Based on the results, it can be seen on table 2 that factor word of mouth get a percentage of 16%. Second, there is factor Customer satisfaction with percentage of 13%. Third, the perceived price factor gains 20% and the service quality factor earns 20%.

Based on the results of the preliminary survey above, four were obtained variables that have the highest value, namely Service Quality, Word of Mouth and Perceived price which will be used as variable independent. For Customer satisfaction will be used as variable moderators. Based on these, make research with the title "The Effect of Service Quality, Word of Mouth and Perceived Price on Purchase Decisions using AC Services moderated by Customer Satisfaction in Households of Jakarta".

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

A. Service quality

Customer satisfaction is the magnitude of a person's sentiment after comparing the performance or results he experiences with his expectations, while service quality is the level of excellence expected and control over the level of perfection to meet customer demands (Fandy Tjiptono, 2011).

B. Word of Mouth

According to (Kotler et al., 2016), word of mouth is a communication strategy that involves offering recommendations for a product or service both individually and in groups with the aim of sharing personal information.

C. Perceived price

According to Lee and Lawson-Body, perceived price are judgments and types of consumer sentiment related to whether the price offered by sellers and prices compared to other parties is reasonable, acceptable, or justifiable (2011: 532).

D. Customer satisfaction

Customer satisfaction is described as "a person's joy or disappointment as a result of comparing perceptions of product performance or results with expectations" (Kotler et al., 2018). According to the microeconomic theory approach, consumer behavior theory argues that every customer will try to get maximum pleasure.

E. Purchase decision

According to Kotler (2011), purchase decisions are activities carried out by customers to decide whether to buy a product or not. Consumers often consider quality, price, and brand reputation among several aspects that influence their purchase of a product or service.

Fig. 2: Framework

III. RESEARCH METHODS

A. Research design

This study includes quantitative research, as well as survey methodology and explanatory tactics. According to Sugiyono (2017), the quantitative method is a positivism-based research approach used to study a particular population or sample, collect data using research tools, then apply quantitative or statistical analysis to evaluate pre-existing assumptions. Quantitative research is defined as research that describes or explains a problem with generalizable conclusions, according to Kriyantono (2012). As a result, the breadth of the data or analysis becomes less important. In order for data or research findings to appear representative of the entire population, researchers pay more attention to the characteristics of the breadth of the data. An explanatory survey is a research technique used when researchers want to understand why certain circumstances or conditions exist or what causes something to happen, according to Kriyantono (2012: 60).

B. Population and Sample

➤ *Population*

According to Ferdinand (2014), the population consists of all elements in the form of objects, events, or individuals that have certain characteristics and are the focus of attention of researchers to support or test certain theories. All household sector clients of PT. Sahabat Karya Teknik who have made purchases by the end of May 2022 are the population of this study.

➤ *Sample*

(Ferdinand, 2014) states that the sample is part of the population consisting of a number of people in the population. Probability sampling will be the sampling method used in this investigation. A sampling method called probability sampling gives every member of the population

an equal chance of being sampled. The formula (Yamane 1973) is used in this study to calculate the sample size of the population. Another formula that can be used is:

$$n = N / 1 + N d^2$$

Researchers use a travel sample using this formula based on the formula above. Calculations lead to the following conclusions:

$$n = \frac{190}{1 + 190 \times (0.01)^2}$$

$$n = \frac{190}{1 + 190 \times 0.0001}$$

$$n = \frac{190}{1.090}$$

$$n = 175 \text{ respondents}$$

These calculations lead to the conclusion that 175 respondents are a population that can be used as a sample.

C. Method of collecting data

The questionnaire given to AC Service respondents is the method used to collect data. Sugiyono (2018) defines a questionnaire as a data collection method in which respondents are given a list of questions or written statements to respond to. Surveys can be closed or open-ended questions or statements and can be distributed in person, by mail or online.

IV. ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

To ascertain how the independent factors jointly affect the dependent variable, the F test is used to determine whether the dependent variable is indeed affected by the regression coefficient of the independent variable or not.

ANOVA ^a

Model		Sum of Squares	df	MeanSquare	F	Sig.
1	Regression	149.107	3	49.702	31.405	.000 ^b
	residual	270.630	171	1.583		
	Total	419.737	174			

Table 3: F Test Results

a. Dependent Variable: Purchase_Decision

b. Predictors: (Constant), Perception_Price, Quality_Service, Word_Of_Mouth

Source: Process data with SPSS 23

The calculated F value of 31.405 with a substantial level of 0.000 is explained in table 1.3. Based on the results of calculations performed with the help of SPSS 23 software, it is known that the value of Sig = (0.000); at a significance level of 0.05, H0 is rejected or the model and data agree. This model is considered valid and can be used for further research because it can be said that the variables of Service Quality, Word of Mouth, Perceived Price, and Customer Satisfaction directly have a large influence on purchase decisions.

A. Test-t results

This test is designed to assess the importance of the independent variable's partial or independent impact on the dependent variable. By using the significant value and t count obtained, this effect can be approximated. to find out whether Customer Satisfaction (Z), Perceived Price (X3), Word of Mouth (X2), and Service Quality (X1) have a substantial effect on Purchase Decision (Y). The following test results were obtained with a significance level of 0.05:

Coefficients ^a

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	std. Error	Betas		
1 (Constant)	2.030	1.050		1.933	.055
Service quality	.010	.060	.010	2.164	.001
Word_Of_Mouth	.109	.055	.170	1.973	.050
Perception_Price	.304	.054	.486	5.632	.000

Table 4: Test-t Results for Model 2

a. Dependent Variable: Customer Satisfaction

Coefficients ^a

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	std. Error	Betas		
(Constant)	1.269	1.147		1.107	.270
Service quality	.108	.066	.102	1.636	.004
Word_Of_Mouth	.085	.060	.125	1.406	.021
Perception_Price	.315	.059	.474	5.355	.000
Satisfaction	.421	.212	.321	2.124	.002

Table 5: Test-t Results for Model 1

a. Dependent Variable: Purchase_Decision

Source: Process data with SPSS 23

The results of the test-t show the effect of the Service Quality variable on purchase decisions seen from a significance value of 0.004 based on the calculation results in Table 1.4 and Table 1.5. Trust is partly understood to have a beneficial and significant influence on the choice to use AC services ($0.004 < \alpha 0.05$). Considering that *the Word of Mouth* variable has a significance value of 0.021 ($0.021 < \alpha 0.05$), it can be concluded that *Word of Mouth* influences purchase decisions positively and significantly.

The significant value of 0.000 indicates that the perceived price factor has a major influence on purchase decisions. Perceived price is partly considered to have a beneficial and substantial impact on purchase decisions ($0.000 < \alpha 0.05$). A significant value of 0.001 indicates that the variable Service Quality has an influence on purchase decisions through customer satisfaction. Partially it can be concluded that Service Quality has a positive and significant effect on Purchase Decisions through Customer Satisfaction ($0.001 < \alpha 0.05$).

A significant result of 0.050 indicates that the word of mouth variable influences consumer satisfaction which leads to purchase decisions. ($0.050 = \alpha 0.05$) is partly understood as an indication that Service Quality significantly and favorably influences purchase decisions. The influence of perceived price variables on consumer satisfaction as measured by purchase choices is quite large at 0.000. Perceived price is partly considered to have a beneficial and substantial impact on purchase decisions ($0.000 = \alpha 0.05$). The value of 0.000 indicates that the satisfaction variable has a strong influence on purchase decisions. Some concluded that satisfaction has a beneficial and substantial impact on purchase decisions ($0.000 < \alpha 0.05$).

B. Coefficient of Determination (R^2)

The ability of a model to explain the variance of the dependent variable is measured by analysis of the coefficient of determination of the adjusted R square (R^2) value.

Summary Model^b

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	std. Error of the Estimate
1	.596 ^a	.755	.344	1.258

Table 6: Test Results for the Coefficient of Determination

Source: Process data with SPSS 23

a. Predictors: (Constant), Perception_Price, Quality_Service, Word_Of_Mouth

b. Dependent Variable: Purchase_Decision

The coefficient of determination R Square is 0.755 based on Table 1.6 above. This shows that the model can only explain 0.755, or 75.5 %, of the variation in the decision to use AC services; the remaining 24.5% is explained by factors not included in this study.

V. CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS**A. Conclusion**

The following conclusions are reached based on research findings and debates on the impact of service quality, word of mouth, perceived price, and satisfaction with purchase decisions:

- The quality of customer service influences purchases in a profitable way. Through the test-t results indicate that Service Quality has a significant effect on consumer purchase decisions.
- Referrals from friends and family influence purchase choices favorably. Through test-t findings, it is shown that word of mouth has a considerable impact on purchase decisions.
- How big a price is considered to have an influence on purchases. Through test-t findings, it is shown that perceived price has a major influence on purchase decisions.
- Customer satisfaction in the service industry has a beneficial impact on purchase decisions. Customer satisfaction is proven to have a large impact on purchase decisions based on the results of the test-t.
- Customer satisfaction makes word of mouth effective in influencing consumer decisions. Through customer satisfaction, word of mouth has been shown to have a considerable impact on purchase decisions based on test-t results.
- Through customer satisfaction, perceived price have a beneficial impact on purchase decisions. Through customer satisfaction, perceived price are proven to have a major influence on purchase decisions based on the results of the test-t.
- Consumer decisions are positively influenced by satisfaction. The test-t findings show that satisfaction has a large impact on purchase decisions.

B. Recommendation

The author tries to offer some recommendations that may be useful and as input for PT. Sahabat Karya Teknik to maintain and improve the decision to purchase AC services based on the analysis carried out during the research and the conclusions that have been stated previously, including:

➤ *Practical Advice*

- To increase sales of air conditioning services, PT. Sahabat Karya Teknik is expected to pay attention to factors related to price perceptions. PT. Sahabat Karya Teknik can provide AC (Air Conditioner) service prices which do not have to be cheap or expensive, but can provide prices that are in accordance with the services provided. In this strategy PT. Sahabat Karya Teknik can make several price packages grouped from those that are classified as cheap, medium and premium, this is to ensure that the services provided by PT. Sahabat Karya Teknik can reach all people from the middle to upper middle class.
- It is suggested to the management of PT. Sahabat Karya Teknik to be able to minimize the risk of complaints that may occur to consumers, especially when AC service is in progress. PT. Sahabat Karya Teknik must be able to provide and improve the services of 24 hours customer service either by calling, by e-mail, or by chatting with customer service staff directly. This can be done by giving surveys or telephone calls to consumers to assess the performance of PT. Sahabat Karya Teknik's services after they use the AC service to be able to find out input from buyers. This is of course as a form of effort to increase customer satisfaction after using AC service services.
- The management of PT. Sahabat Karya Teknik can increase positive reviews by correcting a number of things related to AC service information to other customers. Information regarding PT. Sahabat Karya Teknik's AC service needs to be specified in more detail on the company's website, positive customer testimonials are included and each job has been completed, customers are asked to fill out a short form regarding customer satisfaction. So far this has been done, but it has not been done consistently so that not all customers remember to refer PT. Sahabat Karya Teknik to other potential customers.
- The management of PT. Sahabat Karya Teknik needs to regularly provide training to technicians. The reliability of technicians will further improve the quality of service such as work completed on time and as needed, swift

complaint handling, adequate equipment and honesty of technicians when in the field.

➤ *Academic Advice*

For further research, it is suggested to be able to reexamine the variables and theories that have been used in this study by expanding the research sample by conducting research on big cities in Indonesia which of course have different characteristics, so that different handling is needed related to causing consumer buying decisions on air conditioning services.

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